

Sex differences in early childhood growth in a resource-limited setting: A secondary analysis of the Early Life Interventions in Childhood Growth and Development In Tanzania (ELICIT) study

Mark D. DeBoer, Sarah E. Elwood, James A. Platts-Mills, Elizabeth T. Rogawski McQuade, Joann M. McDermid, Rebecca J. Scharf, Samwel Jatosh, Estomih Mduma

Department of Pediatrics (MDD, RJS) and Division of Infectious Diseases & International Health (SEE, JAPM, ETRQ, JMM, RJS), University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA, USA

Haydom Global Health Research Centre, Haydom Lutheran Hospital, Haydom, Tanzania (SJ, EM),

Corresponding author:

Mark D. DeBoer, MD, MSc., MCR

PO Box 800386

University of Virginia

Charlottesville, VA 22908

Phone: 434-924-5956

Fax: 434-924-9181

Email: [HYPERLINK "mailto:deboer@virginia.edu" }](mailto:deboer@virginia.edu)

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Abbreviations list:

EBF, exclusive breastfeeding; ELICIT, Early Life Interventions for Childhood Growth and Development in Tanzania; HCZ, head-circumference-for-age z-score; LAZ, length-for-age z-score; OR, odds ratio; WAMI, water and sanitation, assets, maternal education and household income; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score

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Data availability statement: Data described in the manuscript, code book, and analytic code will be made available upon request pending application and approval.

1 ABSTRACT

2 Background: In population-based growth surveys in sub-Saharan Africa, boys have higher rates of
3 growth failure than girls.

4

5 Objective: Our goal was to assess for the presence, timing and potential etiology of sex-based
6 differences in length-for-age z-score (LAZ), weight-for-age z-score (WAZ) and head-circumference-for-
7 age z-score (HCZ) in a birth cohort in rural Tanzania.

8

9 Methods: We performed a secondary analysis of RCT data on 1084 children followed from age <2
10 weeks-18 months, assessing anthropometry (measured every 3-months), illness (hospitalization and
11 monthly maternal report of symptoms) and feeding (monthly maternal report of exclusive breastfeeding
12 [EBF] and complementary solids and liquids [CSL]). We used linear regression to assess sex
13 differences in LAZ, WAZ and HCZ over time.

14

15 Results: While male and female infants had similar anthropometry measures at study entry, males
16 exhibited poorer growth through 6-months (e.g., 3-month mean LAZ: males -0.94, females -0.74,
17 $p < 0.01$; 3-month mean WAZ: males -0.63, females -0.48, $p < 0.05$), without significant worsening from 6-
18 18 months. Males had lower HCZ only at 9-months. In evaluating possible etiologies, mediation
19 analysis failed to identify illness or hospitalization as mediators of poorer growth among males, though
20 at age 3-months, males with recently-reported illness exhibited greater decline in WAZ than females
21 with illness (Δ WAZ: males -0.24, females 0.03, heterogeneity test $p = 0.01$). Differences in EBF and
22 introduction of CSL did not explain the sex-based growth outcomes.

23

24 Conclusions: In longitudinal analysis, males exhibited more severe growth failure by 3-months than girls
25 and did not exhibit catch-up growth between 6-18 months. Reported symptoms of illness and early
26 introduction of CSL did not appear to be mediators of these sex-based differences, though likely not all

27 sickness was captured by monthly maternal report. Given the early nature of these deficits, LAZ and
28 WAZ measures at 6-months may be good outcomes for intervention studies targeting improvements in
29 early childhood growth and thriving.

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32 Key Words: sex, growth, stunting, infancy, illness, exclusive breast feeding

INTRODUCTION

Despite gains in early childhood mortality in recent years, undernutrition and infectious diseases persist in low- and middle-income countries and contribute to a high degree of stunting.(1-3) In many but not all areas, the decrements in growth are worse among male compared to female children.(4-10) Under conditions of optimal health and nutrition—such as those used by the World Health Organization in deriving childhood growth curves—male infants have a slightly larger measures of length (by 2-3%) and weight (by 5-8%) in the first 18 months of life.(11) However, in a variety of settings that include nutritional and disease challenges, male infants have a higher prevalence of stunting and wasting. This has been noted in particular in studies in sub-Saharan Africa; a meta-analysis of such studies reported that males (compared to females) had an odds ratio (OR) of 1.18 for stunting,(4) while multiple individual studies over the past 10 years have reported OR of 1.2 - 2.5 for underweight among males compared to females in sub-Saharan Africa.(5-10)

The male-female differences in early-life health outcomes are not limited to growth or to sub-Saharan Africa, as males worldwide have a higher infant mortality rate,(12, 13) which appears largely due to an increase in vulnerability to infections.(12, 14) Sex-based differences in morbidity have also been noted in neonatal intensive care units, where male infants (compared to matched females) have a greater need for ventilator and circulatory support.(15) Based on these differences in growth and other health sequelae, authors have hypothesized that male infants are more susceptible to multiple early life challenges, including nutritional insufficiencies and infectious diseases(12)--though it is not clear whether these are linked or which of these predominate in influencing growth. Other researchers have speculated on the evolutionary underpinnings to these observations,(16) while still others have considered how cultural differences in treatment of different sexes could be involved.(17, 18)

The majority of studies utilized in reporting on sex-based differences in growth in developing areas of the world have been from national demographic and health surveys.(5-9) While these surveys benefit from a nationally-representative group of children with geographic and socioeconomic diversity, they are usually limited to cross-sectional study designs, evaluate children at a range of ages from birth to 5 years and lack measure of additional anthropometry assessments such as head circumference, which may most closely associate with cognitive outcomes.(19) Thus, questions remain about the time of appearance of these anthropomorphic differences and the role of any contributory factors.

Our goal in the current analysis was to assess the timing of any sex-based differences in growth, how these potential differences were manifest across multiple measures of anthropometry (including head circumference), and whether there were relationships between growth variation by sex and measures of infectious disease and feeding practices. We analyzed data from a cohort of children followed longitudinally from 0-18 months in the area around Haydom, Tanzania,(20) a rural region with a high degree of early-life enteric pathogens(21) and food scarcity.(22) We hypothesized 1) that male infants would grow more slowly than females, 2) that growth separation by sex would be more pronounced in weight gain than other anthropometric measures, and 3) that these differences would be associated with males exhibiting a more severe growth response to symptoms of infection but without any sex-based differences in growth related to feeding practices. These data may help in improving understanding of sex-based variation in growth during early life challenges.

METHODS

Study design

The overall study design, participant baseline characteristics, and primary outcomes of the Early Life Interventions for Childhood Growth and Development in Tanzania (ELICIT) study have been reported previously (3, 23, 24). Briefly, this was a 2x2 factorial RCT that assessed effects of two different interventions (daily nicotinamide and scheduled antimicrobials) on childhood growth age 0-18 months. The study protocol was approved by the National Institute for Medical Research of Tanzania, the Tanzanian Medicine and Medical Device Authority and the Institutional Review Board at the University of Virginia. Study oversight was provided by FHI360 (North Carolina, USA). Mothers gave written informed consent to participate either during pregnancy or at the time of enrolment. Inclusion criteria at enrollment were maternal age ≥ 18 years, child age < 14 days and the family's stated intent to reside within a 25-km radius of Haydom Lutheran Hospital for the duration of the study. Exclusion criteria were multiple gestation, significant birth defect or neonatal illness, infant weight < 1500 g at enrollment and lack of intent to breastfeed. The intended target size of 1188 participants was achieved (3). The study was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT03268902.

Interventions

As part of the factorial design, approximately equal groups of participants received either nicotinamide and antimicrobials, placebo for both arms, nicotinamide and placebo, or antimicrobial and placebo. For the nicotinamide intervention, lactating mothers received a nicotinamide 250 mg tablet daily (or placebo) during months 0-6 (with the hypothesis that this would be conferred to the child in the breast milk), and children received sachets of nicotinamide 100 mg (or placebo) mixed in food daily from months 7-18. Nicotinamide and corresponding placebo were manufactured by Vita-gen, New York, USA.

For the antimicrobial intervention, participants received azithromycin or its corresponding placebo (both manufactured by Universal Corp, Kenya) as a single oral dose of 20 mg/kg of 200 mg/5 mL suspension at months 6, 9, 12, and 15. Nitazoxanide or placebo (both by Romark, Florida, USA) was administered as a 3-day course of 100 mg twice daily of 100 mg/5 mL suspension at months 12 and 15.

Study nurses and community healthcare workers received a training program in how to provide families with guidance regarding World Health Organization and Tanzanian Ministry of Health recommendations for exclusive breastfeeding through age 6 months and how to support mothers who may encounter problems with breastfeeding.(25)

Data collection

Study visits occurred at the family's home, both for enrollment and monthly thereafter. Child length, weight, and head circumference were measured at enrollment and every three months thereafter. At these visits, length was assessed using measuring boards, weight was assessed using digital scales, and head circumference was assessed using measuring tape, with additional details described previously.(3, 23) At monthly visits in between these quarterly visits, children had weights

measured by spring scales. At approximately child age of 11 months, mothers' height was measured with a standing stadiometer and weight was measured with a digital scale.

At each monthly visit, mothers responded to questionnaires including items such as infant feeding practices including breastfeeding and complementary food and liquid, child illness symptoms, healthcare utilization and medication use. Breastfeeding status was determined by the mother responding to the following questions, "Since this time yesterday, has this child been breastfed?" and "Since this time yesterday, was breastfeeding the main source of foods?" Mothers were also asked, "Has the mother given any other liquids into the diet now or within the last month?" and "Has the mother given any solid food into the diet now or within the last month?" Children were considered exclusively breastfed if the answers to the first two questions were "yes" and the answers to the second two questions had always been "no." Children were additionally excluded from the exclusive breastfeeding categorization if the mother indicated that the child had received eggs, beans, meat or dairy in the past week. Children were considered predominantly breast fed if the answers to the first two questions were "yes" and the answers to either of second two questions had ever been "yes." Children were considered to have any breastfeeding if the answer to the first question was "yes."

Regarding child health status, the mother was asked at each monthly visit whether in the past week(26) the child had illness, a fever, a cough, or diarrhea. She was also asked whether in the past month the child had received healthcare (including hospitalizations) or taken a non-study medication (which was then identified). Adverse event forms were completed for illness symptoms, and children with current illness symptoms were referred to local healthcare providers. Serious adverse events included hospitalizations and events deemed medically significant by study pediatricians.

At the first monthly visit, mothers responded to questions about demographic and economic factors. Participant socioeconomic status was assessed using a scoring system developed from a prior study (MAL-ED) based on improved water and sanitation, assets, maternal education and household income (WAMI)(27).

Statistical analysis

For the current analysis, we evaluated data from children who had a valid 18-month anthropometry measurement (the modified intention-to-treat group—those who had measurement for 18-month LAZ, the primary outcome). We began by assessing descriptive measures of differences in anthropometry by sex, both for absolute z-score measures quarterly and the change in anthropometry between measurement intervals. We used these data to target our assessment to the first 6 months of life, given relevant inter-sex differences. We used a formal mediation analysis (using the 'mediation' package in R) to assess whether the effect of sex on anthropometry measure was indirectly mediated through any of the illness variables (i.e., whether lower levels of WAZ or LAZ in males as compared to females were related to measures of illness, including hospitalization and illness-related adverse events). Indirect effect estimates were bootstrapped 1,000 times to determine the 95% confidence intervals. We also used unadjusted linear regressions to evaluate whether the associations of markers of illness or supplemental feeding on anthropometry outcomes differed by sex using interaction terms. As a sensitivity analysis, we also adjusted these models for previously-identified predictors of growth (WAMI score, maternal age, maternal height, maternal tribe, maternal education [>7 years vs. <7 years],

birth month, hospital birth, firstborn status, ward of residence(3)). All analyses were conducted using R version 3.6.2.

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics

We analyzed data from 1084 participants (Supplemental Figure 1), including 561 males and 523 females. There were no differences in demographic and maternal features by sex (Supplemental Table 1). Further details regarding overall baseline characteristics and intervention outcomes have been described previously.(3, 24)

Sex differences in anthropometry

Anthropometry measures over time between sexes are shown in Figure 1 A-C. At study entry (age <14 days), males and females had similar mean weights, lengths and head circumference, with growth deficits that were more pronounced for entry LAZ (males -0.83, females -0.77) than for WAZ (males -0.58, females -0.63) or HCZ (males -0.03, females -0.03). Notably, while mean entry weights were not significantly different between sexes, females were more likely to have a low entry weight <2.5 kg (males n=30, 5.34%, females n=56, 10.7%, $p<0.001$).

By age 3 months, females had maintained LAZ and WAZ, while males had a decrease in both of these (3-month LAZ: males -0.94, females -0.74, $p<0.001$; WAZ: males -0.63, females -0.48, $p=0.02$); these differences widened further by 9 months before essentially paralleling each other through 18 months (Figure 1). HCZ levels remained similar through age 3 months, before widening, with females having a greater HCZ at 9 months (males -0.47, females -0.28, $p<0.01$). HCZ for males then increased to that of females by 12-18 months. Covariate adjustment (WAMI score, maternal age, maternal height, maternal tribe, maternal education [>7 years vs. <7 years], birth month, hospital birth, firstborn status, ward of residence—identified previously(3)) did not change these results; for example, male-female difference in 6-month WAZ 0.25 (CI 0.15, 0.36, $p<0.001$).

When subsetting to infants with low entry weight (as a surrogate for low birthweight, <2.5 kg), females began with significantly lower LAZ at study entry (males -1.51, females -1.92, $p=0.02$) but had a higher LAZ by 3 months (males -1.95, females -1.50, $p=0.04$) as well as at 18 months (Supplemental Figure 2). WAZ was initially similar and was only significantly different at 6 months (males -1.59, females -1.12, $p=0.03$). Among this subset of infants with low entry weight, HCZ was not different between sexes through 18 months (Supplemental Figure 2). Adjustment for covariates (listed previously) did not alter the results (data not shown).

Assessed as change in z-score in the overall cohort (Figure 1 D-F), males (compared to females) consistently had a greater decrease in LAZ through age 12 months, though none of those quarterly differences in the change in LAZ were statistically significant individually (Figure 1D). The change in WAZ was significantly more negative among males at 3 months and 6 months before narrowing as the WAZ levels paralleled each other from 9-18 months (Figure 1E). Change in HCZ levels were not significantly

different between groups. Further adjustment for covariates (listed previously) did not alter the results (data not shown).

Analyses for illness as cause of sex-based growth differences

Given prior reports of differences in early-life infections between sexes and having noted that the separation between groups in WAZ in particular (and also LAZ) appeared to occur in the first 6 months of life, we next evaluated for differences in reported illness between males and females from entry through 6 months (Table 1). There was a high number of illness reported overall, which did not differ between sexes (events per person during months 1-6: males 1.05, females 0.98, $p=0.28$). Also similar between sexes were rates of individual symptoms of illness, including fever, cough and diarrhea, as well as use of healthcare and prescribed antimicrobials months 1-6. Males had a higher rate of hospitalization in months 1-6 (males $n=65$ hospitalizations, rate 0.12 per person; females $n=37$, rate 0.07 per person, $p=0.02$).

We next used several analyses to evaluate whether the differences in WAZ and LAZ in the first 6 months were related to illness. In the mediation analysis, there were no significant indirect effects of sex on WAZ or LAZ mediated by either hospitalization or any maternally-reported illness AE (Supplemental Table 2). Further adjustment for covariates (listed above) did not appreciably alter the results (data not shown).

We then evaluated for interactions between illness and sex on WAZ and LAZ (Table 2). In this assessment, there were no statistically significant interactions between sex and markers of sickness for either anthropometry outcome at 3 or 6 months (all heterogeneity tests $p>0.05$). This was also true following adjustment for covariates listed previously (data not shown).

Because we had monthly weight measures and monthly reports on illness, we assessed if there was an interaction between sex and illness on change in WAZ at a more granular monthly basis (Supplemental Table 3). At 2 and 3 months, maternal report of illness over the prior 2 weeks was negatively associated with change-in-WAZ for males (at 2 months, Δ WAZ -0.24 [-0.41, -0.08]; at 3 months -0.24 [-0.39, -0.10]; both $p<0.01$) but not females, though the heterogeneity test for differences in this association between sexes was only significant at 3 months ($p=0.01$). Adjustment for covariates (listed previously) did not alter the results (data not shown).

Analyses for early feeding differences as cause of sex-based growth differences

We next considered whether there were feeding differences between males and females—potentially contributing to growth differences by sex. There was a high rate of exclusive breastfeeding for males and females at 0-6 months, and this did not differ by sex (Table 3). The introduction of complementary liquids was also similar between groups, both in terms of the average age of introduction in months (males 5.99, females 6.14, $p=0.18$) and in the total number of months with complementary liquid supplementation by age 6 months (males 480/3377, females 407/3148). This was similar when looking at introduction of solid food, both by age of introduction (males 6.99, females 6.97, $p=0.83$) and total months provided by age 6 months (males 123/3377, females 96/3148)(Table 3).

In assessing for sex-based differences between exclusive breastfeeding and anthropometry using regression analyses, there was an interaction between sex and the number of months of exclusive breastfeeding in their relationship with LAZ at 3 months and with WAZ at 3 and 6 months, with females (but not males) with longer duration of exclusive breast feeding exhibiting higher anthropometry measures (Table 4). This is to say that males did not receive the same anthropometry-related association of longer exclusive breastfeeding as did females. This appeared related to the introduction of complementary liquids (vs. solids) in that females (but not males) who had introduction of complementary liquids before 3- and 6-months had lower anthropometry measures inverse to those seen for exclusive breastfeeding at the same time points (i.e., for LAZ at 3 months and with WAZ at 3 and 6 months, Table 4). Adjustment for covariates (listed previously) did not appreciably alter the results (data not shown).

DISCUSSION

This study enhances the knowledge of sex-based differences in growth in challenging health settings by following a well-defined longitudinal birth cohort in a rural area in Tanzania with food scarcity and a high prevalence of early-life enteric pathogen carriage.(3, 20-22, 24) We demonstrated an early timing of these sex differences, with males already exhibiting worsened LAZ and WAZ by 3 months, while females had a maintenance or even improvement in growth z-scores during the first 3 months. These differences were perhaps most dramatic among infants with low weight <2.5 kg at study entry, among whom males and females completely reversed relative sex-based deficits in LAZ from study entry to 3 months. A key finding in our analysis was that after age 6 months, the LAZ and WAZ for males and females overall were essentially parallel—suggesting that the more difficult response to challenging conditions among males occurs almost exclusively in early infancy and that affected males do not exhibit catch-up growth by age 18 months. Thus, these data from a longitudinal cohort improve on cross-sectional reports of sex-based growth difference,(5-9) implicating that this separation in growth occurs during this early, vulnerable time before age 6 months as opposed to being spread throughout early childhood. This identifies the first 6 months of life as a time when additional research is critically needed to develop interventions to be deployed in challenging settings to improve growth—with potential interventions including nutritional approaches for mothers during lactation and reduction of infectious disease via decreased exposure or improved treatment. While these interventions are likely to benefit both males and females, the current data suggest it is the males who have a more dire need during this time period. To the degree that growth is a relevant surrogate for other developmental outcomes,(19) our results support that 6-month anthropometry measures may be an efficient end-point for evaluating subsequent pre- and early post-natal interventions.

Unfortunately, despite having a rich amount of data on maternal report of children's symptoms of illness and introduction of complementary nutrition, we were unable to determine the etiology of these sex-based differences in growth. Prior reports have hypothesized that the presence of testosterone in male infants increases susceptibility to infections, potentially contributing to reduced growth.(13) While males in our cohort had a greater rate of hospitalization, they did not exhibit a greater amount of symptoms of illness, and illnesses and hospitalizations did not appear to be mediators of the difference in growth by sex. We did note that at age 3 months, males with reported illness experienced a greater drop in WAZ than did females with illness, though the lack of such interaction

across multiple other time points suggests against this being a pervasive determinant of sex-based differences. Nevertheless, it should be acknowledged that these infants may have experienced significantly more infections than were documented from reported symptoms alone. In particular, intestinal pathogens have been noted from an early age among children in this region, and by far the majority of these did not have concurrent diarrhea that was reported.(21) The same may be true of other early-life pathogens that may be less apparent clinically but may still contribute to growth suppression.(28)

Sex differences in linear growth could also relate to variation in nutrition. Given that the sex-based separation in growth occurs in the first 6 months (when infants are recommended by the WHO to be exclusively breast fed), we were particularly interested in assessing for any relationship between poor growth and the timing of introduction of complementary foods and liquids. We noted sex-based differences in the relationship of LAZ and WAZ and earlier cessation of exclusive breastfeeding stopped. Female but not male infants with longer duration of breastfeeding had higher LAZ and WAZ than those who stopped exclusive breastfeeding earlier—and had an inverse in these relationships with the age at introduction of complementary fluid. This is notable, since introduction of complementary foods and fluids in this timeframe may both result in ingestion of food of lower calorie density than breast milk and can deprive the infant of immune-modulating components of breast milk—at the same time as introducing potential pathogens through contaminated sources of food and liquid. Still, we lacked information on the frequency of breastfeeding on an individual basis to assess whether males or females were fed differently. Also, there is the potential for reverse causation, should families note poor weight gain and elect to provide differential food or fluid sources thinking this might improve nutritional benefit. It is unclear whether any tendency to halt exclusive breastfeeding following weight loss has any difference by sex, for example due to culturally-influenced choices.(17, 18) Thus, the relevance of these sex-based interactions of exclusive breastfeeding with growth is unclear—particularly in a cohort with such a high rate of self-reported exclusive breastfeeding through 6 months.

Mean HCZ did not differ between males and females until age 9 months—and subsequently approximated, with apparent catch-up growth among males. The differences in HCZ are important because HCZ is a noteworthy anthropometric marker of developmental potential.(19) The reason for the timing of this separation in HCZ is unknown, though it has been well described that growth in head circumference is a late indicator of nutritional challenges, lagging behind poor weight gain or linear growth shortfalls.(29) However, it is perhaps surprising that HCZ in males returned to the level seen in females without exhibiting similar improvements in weight or length, supporting the need for further assessments for the presence and timing of HCZ variation in other studies.

This study benefitted from a well-characterized longitudinal cohort evaluated through monthly home visits in a region with known food insecurity and enteric infection risks. We also note several limitations of the study. While evaluations occurred in participants' home on a monthly basis, we only obtained quarterly measures of length, head circumference and weight on a digital scale—overall limiting our ability to look for month-to-month changes in these measures. We relied on maternal report of illness symptoms, exclusive breastfeeding, and introduction of complementary foods—all of which is susceptible to variability between mothers,(30, 31) and we lack more comprehensive and direct assessments of the range of potential infections and feeding frequency.

In conclusion, our assessment of this birth cohort revealed important sex-based differences in early growth, with weight gain and linear growth among males (compared to females) faltering in the first 6 months and failing to catch up by 18 months. That HCZ only differed at 9 months raises questions regarding any potential developmental sequelae for these differences. The etiology behind these differences remains unclear. Reported symptoms of infection were not consistently associated with growth differences, with only a suggestion of males responding to illness with greater weight loss; further assessments of objective markers of infection are still needed. Females had lower weights associated with earlier cessation of exclusive breastfeeding, but this would not explain the greater growth deficits in males. More detailed examination remains necessary to identify underlying causes of these sex-based findings and to understand the biological consequences in the short- and long-term.

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FIGURE LEGEND

Figure 1: Quarterly anthropometry by sex for 1,084 children from study entry (<2 weeks old) to 18 months. A: Length-for-age z-score (LAZ), B: weight for age z-score (WAZ) and C: head circumference-for-age z-score, by sex. D: change-in-LAZ between quarters, E: change-in-WAZ between quarters and F: change-in-HCZ between quarters, by sex. Statistical comparison: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Table 1: Difference by sex in frequency of illness between male and female infants age 1-6 months.

	Males (n = 561) Events (Rate per person per 6 months)	Females (n= 523) Events (Rate per person per 6 months)	Incidence rate ratio (females compared to males)	p value
Disease factors				
Symptoms over the past week:				
Illness (summed months 1-6)	591 (1.05)	515 (0.98)	0.93	0.26
Fever (summed months 1-6)	194 (0.35)	193 (0.37)	1.07	0.53
Cough (summed months 1-6)	368 (0.66)	345 (0.66)	1.01	0.95
Diarrhea (summed months 1-6)	154 (0.27)	121 (0.23)	0.84	0.16
Health care over the past month:				
Received health care (summed months 1-6)	628 (1.12)	544 (1.04)	0.93	0.21
Antimicrobial use (summed months 1-6)	503 (0.9)	447 (0.85)	0.95	0.46
Hospitalization (summed months 1-6)	65 (0.12)	37 (0.07)	0.61	0.02
Adverse event (summed months 1-6)	813 (1.45)	699 (1.34)	0.92	0.11
Adverse event (from diarrhea, dysentery, acute lower respiratory tract infection, sepsis, septicemia, jaundice, fever or hospitalization)	617 (1.10)	520 (0.99)	0.9	0.08

Table 2: Assessment for interaction between sickness and sex in relationship to length-for-age Z-score (LAZ) and weight-for-age Z-score (WAZ) among male and female infants age 0-6 months.¹

	Hospitalization		Illness from AE's	
	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value
LAZ 3 months (n=1,063)				
Sickness (male)	0.26 (-0.13, 0.64)	0.19	0.07 (-0.11, 0.26)	0.44
Sickness (female)	-0.10 (-0.51, 0.31)	0.64	-0.05 (-0.24, 0.14)	0.62
Heterogeneity test		0.22		0.37
LAZ 6 months (n=1,072)				
Sickness (male)	-0.03 (-0.29, 0.24)	0.85	0.01 (-0.18, 0.2)	0.93
Sickness (female)	0.14 (-0.2, 0.48)	0.42	-0.02 (-0.22, 0.17)	0.82
Heterogeneity test		0.46		0.82
WAZ 3 months (n=1,071)				
Sickness (male)	-0.07 (-0.45, 0.3)	0.70	-0.12 (-0.3, 0.05)	0.17
Sickness (female)	-0.1 (-0.5, 0.29)	0.61	0.00 (-0.18, 0.19)	0.99
Heterogeneity test		0.91		0.34
WAZ 6 months (n=1,073)				
Sickness (male)	0.02 (-0.25, 0.28)	0.91	0.01 (-0.17, 0.2)	0.89
Sickness (female)	-0.06 (-0.40, 0.27)	0.71	-0.05 (-0.24, 0.15)	0.64
Heterogeneity test		0.72		0.66

1. Shown are estimates for the association of sickness-related variables (hospitalization, illness-related adverse event [AE]) with LAZ and WAZ at 3- and 6-months and a heterogeneity test for differences in this association between males and females.

Table 3: Time spent exclusively breast feeding and timing of introduction of complementary food and liquid by sex among 1,084 male and female infants age 0-6 months.

Breastfeeding	Males	Females	p value
Months 0-6:			
Exclusive breast feeding; total person time 0-6 months spent exclusively breastfeeding/total person time in months (%)	2865/3377 (84.8)	2717/3148 (86.3)	0.54
Complementary liquids: age in months when first introduced (mean +/- standard deviation)	5.99 +/- 1.84	6.14 +/- 1.8	0.18
Complementary liquids: summed months 1-6/ total person time in months (%)	480/3377 (14.2)	407/3148 (12.9)	0.16
Solid food: age in months when first introduced (mean +/- standard deviation)	6.99 +/- 1.17	6.97 +/- 1.3	0.83
Solid food (summed months 1-6) / total person time in months (%)	123/3377 (3.6)	96/3148 (3.0)	0.19

Table 4: Assessment for interaction between feeding and sex in relationship to LAZ and WAZ among infants age 0-6 months.¹

	Exclusive breastfeeding through 6 months*		Introduction of complementary liquids (age in months)		Introduction of solids (age in months)	
	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value
WAZ 3 months (n=1,071)						
Feeding (male)	-0.01 (-0.27, 0.25)	0.93	0.03 (-0.24, 0.30)	0.83	-0.09 (-0.48, 0.66)	0.75
Feeding (female)	0.47 (0.18, 0.076)	<0.01	-0.48 (-0.8, -0.16)	<0.01	-0.30 (-0.83, 0.24)	0.28
Heterogeneity test		0.02		0.02		0.33
WAZ 6 months (n=1,073)						
Feeding (male)	-0.08 (-0.26, 0.10)	0.37	0.10 (-0.08, 0.29)	0.25	-0.06 (-0.29, 0.16)	0.59
Feeding (female)	0.23 (0.04, 0.41)	0.02	-0.20 (-0.38, -0.01)	0.04	-0.02 (-0.27, 0.22)	0.84
Heterogeneity test		0.02		0.03		0.83
LAZ 3 months (n=1,063)						
Feeding (male)	-0.02 (-0.29, 0.24)	0.86	0.05 (-0.23, 0.33)	0.71	0.38 (-0.21, 0.97)	0.21
Feeding (female)	0.39 (0.09, 0.69)	0.01	-0.40 (-0.72, -0.07)	0.02	0.-0.25 (-0.80, 0.30)	0.38
Heterogeneity test		0.04		0.04		0.13
LAZ 6 months (n=1,072)						
Feeding (male)	0.04 (-0.14, 0.23)	0.64	-0.02 (-0.20, 0.17)	0.85	-0.14 (-0.37, 0.09)	0.23
Feeding (female)	0.12 (-0.07, 0.31)	0.20	-0.10 (-0.29, 0.09)	0.28	0.10 (-0.15, 0.35)	0.44
Heterogeneity test		0.55		0.53		0.17

1. Shown are estimates for the effect size (and 95% confidence intervals) of feeding characteristics (exclusive breast feeding, presence of introduction of complementary liquid or solids) with length-for-age Z-score (LAZ) and weight-for-age Z-score (WAZ) at 3 and 6 months and a heterogeneity test for differences in this association between males and females. Feeding characteristics are for whether the child did (vs. did not) have at least 3- or 6-months of exclusive breast feeding and were complementary liquids or solids introduced before (vs. after) 3- or 6-months. **Bolded values:** p<0.05.

Title: Sex differences in early childhood growth in a resource-limited setting: A secondary analysis of the Early Life Interventions in Childhood Growth and Development In Tanzania (ELICIT) study

First author: DeBoer MD

Online Supplementary Material

Supplemental Table 1: Participant characteristics by sex among 1,084 children in ELICIT.¹

	Overall (n = 1,084) Number (%) or mean +/- std dev	Males (n = 561) Number (%) or mean +/- std dev	Females (n= 523) Number (%) or mean +/- std dev	P value ²
Demographics				
Ward				
Gar	96 (8.85%)	51 (9.09%)	45 (8.6%)	0.07
Get	123 (11.34%)	54 (9.63%)	69 (13.19%)	
Hayder	210 (19.37 %)	109 (19.43%)	101 (19.31%)	
Haydom	69 (6.37%)	27 (4.81%)	42 (8.03%)	
Magh	206 (19.00%)	120 (21.39%)	86 (16.44%)	
Mwanga	152 (14.02%)	77 (13.73%)	75 (14.34%)	
Endamilay	223 (20.57%)	119 (21.21%)	104 (19.89%)	
<i>Other ward</i>	5 (0.46 %)	4 (0.71%)	1 (0.19%)	
WAMI quartile				
SES 1	264 (24.35%)	138 (24.6%)	126 (24.09%)	0.48
SES 2	197 (18.17%)	98 (17.47%)	99 (18.93%)	
SES 3	322 (29.70%)	177 (31.55%)	145 (27.72%)	
SES 4	301 (27.77%)	148 (26.38%)	153 (29.25%)	
WAMI- t-test	0.31 +/- 0.13	0.31 +/- 0.13	0.3 +/- 0.12	0.6
Hospital birth	559 (51.57%)	292 (52.05%)	267 (51.05%)	0.79
Mother's features				
Height	157.31 +/- 5.68	157.38 +/- 5.65	157.24 +/- 5.71	0.69
Weight	54.96 +/- 9.99	55.18 +/- 10.15	54.72 +/- 9.82	0.45
Age	27.89 +/- 6.65	28.03 +/- 6.76	27.76 +/- 6.53	0.5
Schooling				
Mother's years	6.36 +/- 3.03	6.33 +/- 3.07	6.39 +/- 2.99	0.74
Mother >7 years	245 (22.60%)	119 (21.21%)	126 (24.09%)	0.29

Nutrition					
Birth month vs. season					
Jan	163 (15.04%)		76 (13.55%)	87 (16.63%)	0.7
Feb	128 (11.81%)		63 (11.23%)	65 (12.43%)	
Mar	130 (11.99%)		65 (11.59%)	65 (12.43%)	
Apr	93 (8.57%)		52 (9.27%)	41 (7.84%)	
May	87 (8.03%)		48 (8.56%)	39 (7.46%)	
Jun	63 (5.81%)		38 (6.77%)	25 (4.78%)	
Jul	80 (7.38%)		42 (7.49%)	38 (7.27%)	
Aug	54 (4.98%)		27 (4.81%)	27 (5.16%)	
Sep	27 (2.49%)		18 (3.21%)	9 (1.72%)	
Oct	61 (0.56%)		31 (5.53%)	30 (5.74%)	
Nov	70 (6.46%)		38 (6.77%)	32 (6.12%)	
Dec	128 (11.81%)		63 (11.23%)	65 (12.43%)	
Pre-harvest season	619 (57.10%)		305 (54.37%)	314 (60.04%)	0.07

1. Mean \pm standard deviation is shown for continuous variables and number (percentage) for dichotomous variables unless otherwise stated. 2. T-tests or chi-square as appropriate.

Supplemental Table 2: Mediation analysis for causal mediation effects of sex on WAZ and LAZ through illness 1-6 months.¹

	Hospitalization		Illness from AE's	
	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value
LAZ 3 months (n=1,063)				
Indirect effect	0.00 (-0.00, 0.01)	0.96	0.00 (-0.02, 0.02)	0.86
Direct effect	0.14 (0.02, 0.26)	0.02	0.12 (-0.03, 0.28)	0.13
Total effect	0.14 (0.02, 0.26)	0.02	0.12 (-0.03, 0.27)	0.12
Proportion mediated	0.00 (-0.06, 0.09)	0.97	0.02 (-0.51, 0.39)	0.89
LAZ 6 months (n=1,072)				
Indirect effect	-0.00 (-0.01, 0.00)	0.84	-0.01 (-0.04, 0.01)	0.47
Direct effect	0.19 (0.06, 0.31)	<0.01	0.20 (0.03, 0.36)	0.02
Total effect	0.19 (0.06, 0.31)	<0.01	0.19 (0.03, 0.35)	0.03
Proportion mediated	-0.00 (-0.08, 0.03)	0.85	-0.03 (-0.33, 0.09)	0.50
WAZ 3 months (n=1,071)				
Indirect effect	0.00 (-0.03, 0.03)	0.90	0.00 (-0.02, 0.02)	0.96
Direct effect	0.20 (0.06, 0.32)	<0.01	0.12 (-0.03, 0.28)	0.11
Total effect	0.20 (0.06, 0.33)	<0.01	0.13 (-0.03, 0.29)	0.11
Proportion mediated	0.01 (-0.19, 0.15)	0.90	0.03 (-0.39, 0.42)	0.92
WAZ 6 months (n=1,072)				
Indirect effect	-0.00 (-0.03, 0.02)	0.75	-0.00 (-0.03, 0.01)	0.78
Direct effect	0.24 (0.10, 0.37)	<0.001	0.21 (0.05, 0.38)	0.01
Total effect	0.23 (0.10, 0.37)	<0.001	0.21 (0.05, 0.38)	0.01
Proportion mediated	-0.01 (-0.17, 0.10)	0.75	-0.01 (-0.18, 0.09)	0.78

Abbreviations and explanations:

LAZ, length-for-age z-score; WAZ, weight-for-age z-score.

1. Mediation analysis analyzed the following terms:

Indirect Effect—Average indirect effect of sex (being a girl) on LAZ at 3 or 6 months or WAZ at 3 or 6 months THROUGH the mediator (either diarrhea and/or hospitalization, the aggregate of maternal report of diarrhea and the number of hospitalizations, or illness which is the aggregate variable from the Adverse Event forms that subsets adverse events to diarrhea, dysentery, acute lower respiratory infection, sepsis, septicemia, jaundice, fever or hospitalization.

Direct Effect—Average direct effects. Simply, the direct effect of sex (being a girl) on LAZ at 3 or 6 months or WAZ at 3 or 6 months.

Total Effect—Direct plus indirect effect of sex on anthropometry outcomes

Proportion Mediated—the proportion of the effect of sex on the anthropometry outcomes that is mediated by our illness variables. It's the Indirect Effect divided by the Total Effect.

Supplemental Table 3: Assessment for interaction between illness and sex in relationship to monthly measures of weight-for-age z-score among male and female children age 0-6 months (WAZ).¹

	Illness from maternal report	
	Estimate (95% confidence interval)	p-value
0-1 month (n=1,057)		
Illness (male)	-0.03 (-0.23, 0.17)	0.75
Illness (female)	-0.07 (-0.29, 0.14)	0.49
Heterogeneity test		0.78
1-2 month (1,057)		
Illness (male)	-0.24 (-0.41, -0.08)	<0.01
Illness (female)	-0.15 (-0.34, 0.04)	0.13
Heterogeneity test		0.46
2-3 month (n=1,060)		
Illness (male)	-0.24 (-0.39, -0.10)	<0.01
Illness (female)	0.03 (-0.12, 0.17)	0.73
Heterogeneity test		0.01
3-4 month (n=1,055)		
Illness (male)	-0.09 (-0.21, 0.03)	0.14
Illness (female)	-0.06 (-0.19, 0.07)	0.36
Heterogeneity test		0.74
4-5 month (n=1,058)		
Illness (male)	0.00 (-0.15, 0.14)	0.97
Illness (female)	-0.12 (-0.27, 0.03)	0.12
Heterogeneity test		0.28
5-6 month (n=1,057)		
Illness (male)	-0.04 (-0.16, 0.08)	0.53
Illness (female)	-0.08 (-0.21, 0.05)	0.25
Heterogeneity test		0.68

1. Shown are estimates for the effect size of maternal report of illness within the prior 2 weeks (asked at monthly study visits) and change in WAZ between that time point and the prior monthly study visit. Results are shown for males and females and a heterogeneity test for differences in this association between males and females. **Bolded values:** p<0.05.